

Engineering and
Physical Sciences
Research Council

Incorporation of high-fidelity experimental data into finite element models for enhanced comparison and analysis

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Digital element correlation (DIC)

$u \ v \ w$
 $\epsilon_1 \ \epsilon_2$
 $x \ y \ z$

Demonstrator part: C-spar

DIC setup

MatchID

Metrology beyond colors

Test Rig & eccentricity

Shell FE setup

Hashin damage + energy-based evolution

Problem identification

Delamination not
accounted for

Can we get a
better prediction?

*Do we trust the
manufactured
geometry?*

*Do we trust the
applied loading
eccentricity?*

DIC geometry

$$\begin{matrix} u & v & w \\ \varepsilon_1 & \varepsilon_2 & \\ \hline x & y & z \end{matrix}$$

● DIC surface cloud points ● Shell mesh nodal position

Projection and interpolation
codes adapted from:

https://github.com/carl-scarth/Align_FE_DIC

Wrinkles

Fiducial points

Processing projected geometry for use in FE

Extracted spar geometry from DIC and CT

CAD DIC CT

*Taken at first
frame of DIC*

*Taken before
bonding to
the end caps*

Effect of spar geometry

Effect of spar geometry: Analysis

- CT scans tend to be the most reliable
- Bow-type geometry occurs in all DIC geometries
- Bow-type geometry occurs in pre-clamp as well
- Left and right camera stitching
- Thickness distribution not considered in surface data
- Speckle pattern paint thickness
- Resin potting process into end-block
- DIC optical artefact

DIC boundary condition (BC): Displacement extraction

DIC BC: Displacement smoothing

Nodal displacements before curve fitting

Nodal displacement after curve fitting

DIC BC: Reaction force

Nodal reaction force against true distance

Effect of DIC BC (using CAD geom)

Effect of boundary conditions: Analysis

- DIC nodal displacements are generally accurate and reliable
- Force-displacement graph from DIC BC closely resembles the designed RP BC
- Camera stitching is mostly done within MatchID; Spar 2 is stitched manually
- Smoothing not applied to frames/time
- Residual geometric mismatches
- Other: no delamination prediction, material property uncertainty, no rotational constraints, shorter spar

Conclusion

Realistic shell geometry
using DIC and CT Data

Applying DIC displacement
as FE boundary conditions

CerTest: Multi-scale 2nd order homogenisation

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Thank you!

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